

Supporting
European Cities by
promoting effective
circular solutions

3 Living labs:

AMSTERDAM (NL)

EGALEO (EL)

HAMBURG (DE)

Project partners

STADTREINIGUNG.HAMBURG

Get in touch!

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From
Biowaste
to soil
regeneration

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Why do we need to act?

30% of Municipal waste is biowaste

80% of the biowaste is landfilled or incinerated

These are precious resources..

..that can be turned into very much needed soil improvers

65% of European soils are unhealthy

17% of biowaste is recycled and just a fraction used to improve soils

The approach of the Bin2Bean project:
defining the best solutions for your city

In practice..

1. Local stakeholders will identify the best replicable solutions in terms of biowaste collection and soil improvers production
2. Partners will test methods to demonstrate the safety of soil improvers, and indicators for soil quality
3. Issue of guidelines for policymakers to improve biowaste collection and favor the adoption of soil improvers